

Socio-Demographic Distribution of Hypertension Status Among Adult Traders in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined association between selected socio-demographic characteristics of traders and hypertension. A descriptive cross-sectional design was adopted in this study. The study population consisted of adult traders in the Ibadan metropolis, Nigeria. The sample consisted of 596 respondents from the three major tribes in six major markets in Ibadan metropolis. The sample for the study was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. Demographic variables measures were taken using an inventory to determine respondent age, sex, marital status, ethnicity, religion, number of children and number of years in business while weighing scale and measuring tape for height were used to measure weight and height and sphygmomanometer was used to determine their hypertension status. The frequency distribution of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents was tabulated while chi-square analysis was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study revealed that the socio-demographic characteristics related with hypertension are age, marital status, number of children, number of years in business, body mass index while sex and ethnicity were not related with hypertension. It was recommended that those at higher risk of hypertension should be adequately educated on what and what not to do. There is also an urgent need to educate traders to know their health status and to monitor their blood pressure regularly for early detection of hypertension and prompt treatment given.

IJARBAS

Accepted 15 June 2021
Published 22 June 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5015973

Keywords: Socio-demographic, Hypertension Status, Traders,

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Introduction

Hypertension is an important global public health challenge and a major predisposing factor for heart failure, kidney failure and stroke in sub-Saharan Africa. It is also a major predisposing factor for coronary artery disease, which is currently evolving in sub-Saharan Africa. Uncomplicated essential hypertension is often an asymptomatic ailment, and affected persons in rural sub-Saharan Africa, where poverty and illiteracy are widespread, are often not aware of having hypertension. Such patients in Sub-Saharan Africa usually present for the first time in hospitals with major complications (Ajayi, et al., 2014). According to Oladoyinbo, et al (2015), market traders spend most hours of the day sitting down and involved in many other sedentary activities, conditions that increase the risk of chronic diseases as a result of obesity. They also stated that recent global figures indicate that the prevalence of obesity is not just a problem of the developed countries but is also on the increase in the developing world and that 65% of the world's populations live in countries where overweight and obesity kill more people than underweight (WHO, 2014). In Nigeria, the risk of hypertension is about two times higher among obese individuals than those with normal body weight (Ekanem, et al., 2013).

Several socio-demographic factors are predisposing to hypertension. These factors vary from country to country and even there is a difference between urban and rural regions of the same place. Realizing the effect of urbanization on our collective health, the World Health Organization has chosen "Urbanization and Health" as the theme for World Health Day 2010 (Vincent-Onabajo, et al. 2017). Urban people are more at risk of these diseases as compared to their rural counterparts. According to the findings of the National Family Health Survey (Oguizu, et al 2019), the prevalence of hypertension, obesity, and blood glucose in an urban area of Uttar Pradesh was 10.5%, 23.9%, and 9.9%, respectively. However, the prevalence of the same phenomenon was 8.3%, 10.8%, and 8.2%, respectively in rural areas. All the parameters are having a higher prevalence in urban areas as compared to rural areas. To take effective prevention measures, identification of the risk factors is an essential prerequisite.

With the economic downturn in Nigeria, market traders appear to be at the receiving end especially as their livelihood depends on the purchasing power of shoppers and buyers, in addition to their susceptibility to other adverse factors in the country's socio-economic environment. Thus, market traders often undergo a considerable amount of stress to make ends meet and constitute one of the groups of individuals with the highest work hours. Additionally, market traders in Nigeria, like many other workers in the country's informal sector, often do not have access to structured workplace preventive and curative health programs and services. It is instructive that these scenarios may all be implicated in the risk of developing hypertension (Vincent-Onabajo, et al, 2017).

According to Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research (MFMER) (2018), the risk of high blood pressure increases as you age. Until about age 64, high blood pressure is more common in men while women are more likely to develop high blood pressure after age 65. Some ethnic groups are more prone to hypertension (Isara & Okundia, 2015) while the lifetime risk is the same for males and females, but men are more prone to hypertension at a younger age. The prevalence tends to be higher in older women (Isara & Okundia, 2015). World Health Organization (2014) reported that the prevalence of raised blood pressure (Hypertension), in adults more than 25 years was 38.6% for males and 41.2% for females in Nigeria. Oguizu, Utah-Iheanyichukwu, and Ibejide (2019) conducted a study on the prevalence of hypertension among the adult traders in some selected market in Awka, their findings showed that the prevalence of hypertension at chronic stages (stage 2 and 3) was found to be slightly higher in males (13.6%) than in females (11.4%). The inconsistent in

findings prompted the researcher to examine association between selected socio-demographic characteristics of traders and hypertension.

Research Hypothesis

The following research hypotheses were postulated for this study:

1. There is no association between selected socio-demographic characteristics of traders and hypertension

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional design was adopted in this study. The study population consisted of adult traders in the Ibadan metropolis, Nigeria. The sample consisted of 596 respondents from the three major tribes in six major markets in Ibadan metropolis. The sample for the study was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. Demographic variables measures were taken using an inventory to determine respondent age, sex, marital status, ethnicity, religion, number of children and number of years in business while weighing scale and measuring tape for height were used to measure weight and height and sphygmomanometer was used to determine their hypertension status. Four (4) research assistants per market were recruited for the study, making a total of twenty-four (24) research assistants. Data collected were analysed quantitatively and processed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. The frequency distribution of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents was tabulated while chi-square analysis was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency 596 (%)
Age groups (Years)	
< 40	347 (58.2)
≥ 40	249 (41.8)
Sex	
Male	384 (64.4)
Female	212 (35.6)
Marital status	
Single	199 (33.4)
Married	387 (64.9)
Widow/er	10 (1.7)
Ethnicity	
Yoruba	260 (43.6)
Igbo	200 (33.6)
Hausa	136 (22.8)
Religion	
Christian	308 (51.7)
Islam	288 (48.3)
No of children	
< 4 children	376 (62.9)
≥ 4 children	221 (37.1)
No of years in business	
< 20 years	440 (73.8)
≥ 20 years	156 (26.2)

Table 1 above shows that 347 (58.2%) of respondents were below 40years of age while 249 (41.8%) were 40years and above. 64.4% were male while 35.6% were female. 33.4% of the respondents were single, 64.9% were married while 1.7% widow and widower. This shows that majority of the respondents are married. The distribution of the respondents based on educational status revealed that 14.9% did not attend formal education, 21.0% attended primary education, 54.0% attended secondary education while 10.1% attended tertiary institutions. This shows that the majority of respondents passed through secondary school. 43.6% of respondents were Yorubas, 33.6% were Igbos while 22.8% were Hausas. 51.7% were Christians while 48.3% Moslems. Respondents' distribution on family settings indicates that 67.1% were from monogamous families, 14.8% were from polygamous family while 18.1% did not respond to it. 62.9% of the respondents' have less than 4 children while 37.1% have more than 4 children. 73.8% has been in the business for less than 20years while 26.2% has to be in it for 20years and above.

Figure i: Categories of respondents' body mass index

The figure i above shows that 17 (2.9%) of respondents were underweight, 273 (45.8%) has a normal weight, 194 (32.6%) were overweight while 112 (18.8%) were obese.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no association between selected socio-demographic characteristics of traders and hypertension

Table 2: Association between respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and hypertension status

Variables	Hypertension Status		X ²	df	P-value	Remark
	Not hypertensive	Hypertensive				
Age group (Years)						
< 40	321 (92.5%)	26 (7.5%)	23.99	1	0.0001	Significant
≥ 40	196 (78.7%)	53 (21.3%)				
Sex						
Male	340 (88.5%)	44 (11.5%)	3.03	1	0.082	Not

Female	177 (83.5%)	35 (16.5%)				Significant
Marital status	183 (92.0%)	16 (8.0%)				
Single	329 (85.0%)	58 (15.0%)	17.46	2	0.0001	Significant
Married	5 (50.0%)	5 (50.0%)				
Widow/er						
Ethnicity						
Yoruba	226 (86.9%)	34 (13.1%)				
Igbo	168 (84.0%)	32 (16.0%)	2.93	2	0.231	Not significant
Hausa	123 (90.4%)	13 (9.6%)				
No of children						
< 4 children	338 (90.1%)	37 (9.9%)	10.10	1	0.001	Significant
≥ 4children	179 (81.0%)	42 (19.0%)				
No years in business						
< 20years	393 (89.3%)	47 (10.7%)	9.68	1	0.002	Significant
≥ 20years	124 (79.5%)	32 (20.5%)				
Body mass index						
Underweight	16 (94.1%)	1 (5.9%)				
Normal	252 (92.3%)	21 (7.7%)	15.92	3	0.001	Significant
Overweight	157 (80.9%)	37 (19.1%)				
Obese	92 982.1%)	20 (17.9%)				

Table 2 above, shows that there was statistically significant association between respondents' age group and hypertension status [$p < 0.05$, ($p = 0.0001$)]. The result further shows that a higher proportion of older traders 53 (21.3%) were found to be more hypertensive compared to younger traders 26 (7.5%) prevalence.

From the same table, it has been established that there was no statistically significant association between respondents' sex and hypertension status [$p < 0.05$, ($p = 0.082$)]. It was also observed that female respondents' 35 (16.5%) are more likely to be hypertensive than a male counterpart with 44 (11.5%) prevalence.

The table also revealed that there was a statistically significant association between respondents' marital status and hypertension [$p = 0.05$, ($p = 0.0001$)]. It further revealed that a higher proportion of widow/widower 5 (50.0%) was found to be more hypertensive compared to the single 16 (8.0%) and married traders 58 (15.0%). This suggests that the labor of two persons is handled by one person which leads to the risk of hypertension.

The result also affirmed that there was no statistically significant association between respondents' ethnicity and hypertension status [$p = 0.05$, ($p = 0.231$)]. Though a higher proportion of Igbo traders 32 (16.0%) are more hypertensive compared to other tribes, Yoruba 34 (13.1%) and Hausa 13 (9.6%) due to their socio-cultural belief. For example, a full grown-up Igbo man is expected to have his own house before he gets married. This prompted him to struggle harder to establish himself. This orientation is difference from other tribes in Nigeria.

The same table also revealed that there was a statistically significant association between the number of children given birth by the respondents and hypertension status [$p=0.05$, ($p=0.001$)]. The result further revealed that those respondents with ≥ 4 children 42 (19.0%) are more likely to be hypertensive than those respondents with < 4 children 37 (9.9%). The result of this study suggests that those traders with more number of children have more responsibilities.

This same table also established that there was a statistically significant relationship between some years a trader spent in the business and hypertension status [$p=0.05$, ($p=0.002$)]. The result also shows that the proportion of respondents' that spent ≥ 20 years in business 32 (20.5%) are more hypertensive compared to those that spent < 20 years with 47 (10.7%) prevalence.

It was also affirmed that there was a statistically significant relationship between the respondents' body mass index and hypertension status [$p=0.05$, ($p=0.001$)]. The result further shows that the proportion of respondents that are overweight 37 (19.1%) are more hypertensive compared to others with underweight 1 (5.9%), normal weight 21 (7.7%) and obese 20 (17.9%) prevalence.

Discussion

The findings revealed that the traders who were older ≥ 40 years were more hypertensive than the younger traders. This is because as individual progresses in age, the likelihood of becoming hypertensive is high. This study was consistent with Aghaji (2018) who found out that the hypertension rate among traders increased with increasing age. The study carried out by Ulasi et al (2011) supported these findings too.

The study also revealed that the gender of the traders was not statistically significant but the result further revealed that female traders have higher prevalence of hypertension compared to the male counterpart. This is in line with the finding of Oguizu et al (2019), who found out that female traders were more hypertensive than male traders. The reason is that women are more obese than men. The result of this study was not consistent with the finding of Wordu and Akusu (2018) who found out that hypertension was significantly higher in males than in female respondents. Wordu's finding was supported by Oladoyinbo et al (2015) who revealed that hypertension is more prevalent in male than female. The finding was not supported by Aghaji (2018) who also found out that the prevalence of hypertension among traders in Enugu was 39.5% and it did not vary by gender.

The result also revealed that marital status was statistically significant with hypertension as the widows and widowers have a higher prevalence of hypertension compared to single and married. This could be as a result of greater responsibilities which mount excessive stress on them. This finding was in agreement with Aghaji (2018) who affirmed that hypertension prevalence was highest in respondents who were separated, divorced or widowed and lowest in the unmarried.

The study further revealed that number of children was found to be statistically significant with hypertension as the traders with ≥ 4 children were found to be more hypertensive compared to those with < 4 children. This suggested that the traders with more number of children have more responsibility because the needs of children are highly demanding. Those who could not meet up with their needs are exposed to psychological problem which may eventually lead to hypertension. According to Onigbinde (2001), he affirmed that certain conditions such as obesity, diabetes mellitus, and psychological stress have been associated as risk factors for hypertension.

The result also showed that number of years was statistically significant as the traders who spent ≥ 20 years in business were found to be more hypertensive. This suggests they have undergone vigorous activities that exposed them to the risk of hypertension.

The study affirmed that overweight and obese traders had the higher prevalence of hypertension. The result was in line with Awosan, et al (2013) who revealed high prevalence of overweight and obesity in their study. Isara and Okundia (2015) also found out that in Nigeria, the risk of hypertension is about two times higher among obese than those with normal body weight. This study was compared with the report of 31.3% and 16.3% prevalence of overweight and obesity, respectively, among female traders in Ibadan, Nigeria according to Balogun and Owoaje (2007). This could be related to the high prevalence of unhealthy eating habits and sedentary lifestyle among the participants in the study. This finding was also supported by Oladoyinbo et al (2015) who found out that the prevalence of overweight and obesity among traders in Ijebu-Ode were 25.3% and 26.7%. Obesity and hypertension among market men and women constitute health issues of public health importance. Therefore, traders who were obese and overweight should be advised to avoid sedentary lifestyle by engaging in exercise, recreational activities and also reduce the number of hours sitting in a place. They should also check their body weight and blood pressure regularly.

Implications of the findings

The findings of this study are important for policy formulation and implementation. Findings demonstrated that there was statistically significant association between age group, marital status, number of children, number of years in business, body mass index and hypertension status. The older respondents were mostly affected by hypertension in ≥ 40 years. It means a regular check of blood pressure is very important to every adult.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that the socio-demographic characteristics related with hypertension are age, marital status, number of children, number of years in business, body mass index while sex and ethnicity were not related with hypertension. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that traders should be educated by healthcare workers on socio-demographic characteristics predisposing the risk of hypertension. Those at higher risk of hypertension should be adequately educated on what and what not to do. There is also an urgent need to educate traders to know their health status and to monitor their blood pressure regularly for early detection of hypertension and prompt treatment given.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), EZEIKE, Chinyere Edith (RN, RM, BNSc, PGDE, MPH) AND UKWUOMA, Sunday Ifeanyi (B.Sc., M.Sc., Ph.D in view), (2021). "Socio-Demographic Distribution of Hypertension Status Among Adult Traders in Oyo State, Nigeria". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 78-87. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5015973>, Special Issue: 6, Vol.: 3, Article: 6, Month: June, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

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